

The impact of filtration systems on the survival rate of juvenile horseshoe crabs in laboratory environments

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Abstract

In recent years, the number of Malaysian *Tachypleus gigas* have been declining. The main reason for this phenomenon is the poor water quality of its habitats. Water quality is the main environmental factor that affects *T. gigas*' survival rate. Understanding and improving the water quality is important to increase the survival rate of *T. gigas*. In order to increase the survival rate and reduce the mortality rate of *T. gigas*, we designed a self-made filtration system and grouped it Experiment. To make a comparison, we set up another system with a protein skimmer and grouped it Control. At the end of February to early March 2024, we spent 15 days observing and comparing the water quality and survival rate of juvenile *T. gigas* of both systems, then recorded the data. The mortality rate of Experiment remains low and the water quality was better in Experiment compared to Control. This means that the objective of the experiment was achieved and the hypothesis was accepted, the self-made filtration system was proven effective.

Keywords: *T. gigas*, survival rate, filtration system, water quality

1. Introduction

Horseshoe crabs are marine arthropods. They have existed on Earth since the Ordovician period, with fossils dating back 475 million years, hence the common term "living fossil." Currently, only four species of horseshoe crabs remain in the world: the American horseshoe crab (*Limulus polyphemus*), distributed from the east coast of North America to the Gulf of Mexico; the Chinese horseshoe crab (*Tachypleus tridentatus*), the southern horseshoe crab (*Tachypleus gigas*), and the round-tailed horseshoe crab (*Carcinoscorpius rotundicauda*) (Zhu et al., 2020). Horseshoe crab blood oxidizes to a blue colour upon exposure to air owing to the presence of copper ions, and it possesses antibacterial, antitumour as well as antiviral properties, thus being used in the production of *Limulus* ameobocyte lysate (LAL) for medical testing (Bao et al., 2020).

Among the four horseshoe crab species, the southern horseshoe crab is the most common species in Malaysia. However, as a result of pollution, overfishing, and habitat loss, the local southern horseshoe crab population is gradually declining (Halim et al., 2021). The decline in horseshoe crab populations is not only a wake-up call for the survival of the species itself, but also has an impact on the ecosystems in which they inhabit. One underlying factor contributing to this decline is the issue of habitat water quality. The inadequacy of traditional filtration systems in handling the various pollutants present in aquatic environments underscores the need for innovative methods. However, most current academic research focuses on the natural and anthropogenic factors leading to the horseshoe crab decline and the medical applications of their blood, thus lacking a definitive solution to address water quality issues for horseshoe crab survival. Therefore, our group began designing and building a novel filtration system in November 2023. The purpose of this system was to increase the survival rate of southern horseshoe crabs and reduce their infection rate as well as mortality while minimising the cost of purchasing a protein skimmer. Starting in February 2024, our group spent 15 days comparing the water quality and survival rate of horseshoe crabs in tanks equipped with a self-made filtration system and tanks equipped with a protein skimmer. Both systems used the same type of tank and an air pump, with approximately equal water volume and quality.

The only difference between the two groups was the type of filtration system used. A self-made filtration system was used for the experimental group, while a traditional filtration system, a protein skimmer in this case, was used for the control group. This study hypothesised that the homemade filtration system will reduce the mortality rate and increase the survival rate of the horseshoe crabs in our group.

2.Literature review

2.1 Significance of horseshoe crabs

Horseshoe crabs (order: Xiphocacti) play a crucial ecological role in coastal ecosystems, making them a subject of significant research interest in recent years (Mattei et al., 2022). Their eggs are an important food source for migratory birds during their annual stopover on the east coast of North America (Bopp, 2021). These birds rely on energy-rich eggs to fuel their long journeys, making horseshoe crabs an indispensable part of the migratory food chain (Harlan et al., 2024; Kwan et al., 2020; Botton et al., 2022). Furthermore, horseshoe crabs act as ecosystem engineers by promoting sediment aeration and nutrient cycling through burrowing (Allen et al., 2021). Their burrows enhance sediment oxidation, contributing to the survival of various benthic organisms and influencing overall sediment composition (Deldicq et al., 2021). In addition, studies have found that horseshoe crabs play a role in controlling certain biological populations through predation, such as the invasive green crab (*Carcinus maenas*) (McMahan et al., 2018). Other than that, horseshoe crabs have made significant contributions to the biomedical field, particularly in biomedical research and drug quality testing (Tinker-Kulberg et al., 2020). Their blue blood contains a unique compound called Limulus amoebocyte lysate (LAL), used to detect bacterial endotoxins in pharmaceuticals and medical devices (Tinker-Kulberg et al., 2020; Laffoley et al., 2020). LAL/TAL assays derived from horseshoe crab blood are used to ensure the safety and quality of intravenously administered drugs and vaccines (Gorman, 2020). However, the biomedical industry's reliance on horseshoe crabs for LAL/TAL extraction poses a significant threat to the species' survival (Botton et al., 2022; John et al., 2020). Therefore, maintaining horseshoe crab populations is crucial for biodiversity (Shi et al., 2024). At the same time, comprehensive research efforts are essential to explore alternative methods and technologies with the hope of reducing reliance on horseshoe crabs and ensuring their conservation while meeting the needs of the biomedical field (Bhattacharjee et al., 2023).

2.2 Horseshoe Crab Mortality Factors

The mortality of horseshoe crab is a complex phenomenon influenced by a variety of interconnected factors. Habitat loss stemming from coastal development and climate change is a significant threat (Botton et al., 2022). Rising sea levels and alterations in temperature as well as salinity can disrupt breeding and molting patterns, rendering horseshoe crabs more vulnerable to predators and diseases (Botton et al., 2022). Human activities, such as overharvesting for the biomedical industry and accidental bycatch in fishing gear, also directly contribute to horseshoe crab mortality (Botton et al., 2022). Therefore, understanding and addressing these multifaceted threats are essential for the conservation of horseshoe crab populations.

2.3 Filtration Systems in Aquatic Ecosystems

Traditional filtration systems in aquatic ecosystems have been primarily designed to remove particulate matter and chemical pollutants. However, these systems may not effectively address emerging contaminants and pollutants that pose risks to horseshoe crab survival (Issac et al., 2021). The limitations of traditional filtration systems highlight the need for innovative approaches capable of providing comprehensive water quality management.

2.4 Impact of Filtration Systems on Aquatic Fauna

While filtration systems play a crucial role in maintaining water quality, their impact on aquatic fauna, especially invertebrates like horseshoe crabs, is not well-explored. Studies on the effects of filtration systems on other marine organisms suggest potential ecological consequences (Issac et al., 2021). The introduction of novel filtration technologies may alter the composition of microorganisms and nutrients in the water, indirectly influencing horseshoe crab food sources and overall ecosystem dynamics (Kwan et al., 2023).

2.5 Addressing Research Gaps

Despite the significance of horseshoe crab mortality and the role of filtration systems, there is a notable gap in the existing literature regarding the specific effects of new filtration technologies on horseshoe crab

populations. Most studies have focused on the broader factors contributing to horseshoe crab decline, leaving a knowledge void regarding the potential benefits or drawbacks of advanced filtration systems.

2.6 The Current Study

This research aims to fill this gap by systematically investigating the influence of a new filtration system on horseshoe crab mortality rates. By assessing the efficacy of this technology in mitigating known threats and understanding its potential unintended consequences, the study endeavours to provide a nuanced perspective on the role of filtration systems in the conservation of horseshoe crabs and their ecosystems.

In summary, the reviewed literature underscores the complexity of horseshoe crab mortality factors, the limitations of traditional filtration systems, and the need for research specifically addressing the impact of innovative filtration technologies on horseshoe crab populations.

3. Methodology

3.1 Preparation

3.1.1 Assembly of Filtration System

Two filtration systems were utilised in this study. Specifically, a self-made filtration system was used for the experimental group while a Dophin PS2012 protein skimmer was used for the control group.

Regarding the self-made filtration system in experimental group, materials needed included sand, two filter screens, a plastic bucket, plastic water pipes, a faucet, cloth, ten scouring pads, pebbles of various sizes, a water tank, and a water pump. A hole was drilled in the plastic bucket, 5cm from the bottom and 4cm from the top. A 3mm plastic water pipe and a 3.5mm faucet were connected to the holes. The pipes were wrapped with sealing tape to ensure a tight connection and prevent leaks. A filter screen, cloth, ten scouring pads, and pebbles were added to the bucket until it was 7cm from the top of the filter bucket. The plastic water pipes of the filtration system were connected to a water tank. 1cm to 1.5cm layer of sand was added. A Dophin P-150 water pump was connected. As precaution steps, the other filter screen was used to cover the water pump in order to prevent blockage by sand, which impairs operation. Besides, a plastic sheet was used to cover the outlet of the water pipe leading to the basin to slow the water flow in order to prevent adverse effects on the horseshoe crabs.

Figure 1 Illustration of Self-made Filtration System

(*Note: filter screen and plastic sheet used in precaution steps are excluded)

Regarding the control group, assemble the Dophin PS2012 protein skimmer according to the instructions stipulated in its product manual and place it on the side of another water tank. Connect the oxygen pump. As precaution step, place a small transparent bowl over the power head of the protein skimmer in order to prevent horseshoe crabs from adhering to it.

3.1.2 Salt Water Preparation

Sixteen tanks were used, each containing 3.8 liters of tap water (60.8 liters in total), which was left to stand for three days to dechlorinate. Dechlorination is necessary as recent studies have shown that chlorine concentrations above 0.03 ppm are harmful to aquatic life, and the chlorine concentration in tap water is generally in the range of 4.0 ppm to 8.0 ppm (Kasper et al., 2022). In the preparation of the salt solution, the following salinity formula was used to accurately obtain the mass of sea salt required to prepare salt water with a salinity of 27 ppt.

Original formula:

$$\text{Salinity} = \frac{\text{Mass of Dissolved Salt}}{\text{Volume of Water}} \times 1000$$

After rearrangement,

$$\text{Mass of Dissolved Salt} = \frac{\text{Salinity} \times \text{Volume of Water}}{1000}$$

In the formula, the mass of dissolved salt is expressed in kg, the volume of water in L, and the salinity in ppt. During the measurement process, an electronic scale was used to measure the mass of salt in g, accurate to two decimal places. A measuring cylinder was used to measure the volume of water in ml, accurate to 10 ml. The calculation is as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Volume of water in each tank} &= 3800 \text{ ml} \\ &= 3.8 \text{ L} \end{aligned}$$

Salinity required for each tank of water = 27 ppt

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mass of Dissolved Salt} \\ &= \frac{\text{Salinity} \times \text{Volume of Water}}{1000} \\ &= \frac{27 \times 3.8}{1000} \\ &= 0.1026 \text{ kg} \\ &= 102.6 \text{ g} \end{aligned}$$

∴ 102.6 g of salt is needed to prepare 3.8 L of salt water with a salinity of 27 ppt.

30.4 L of salt water with a salinity of 27 ppt was added into the water tank used in experimental group and control group respectively.

3.1.3 Environmental Adaptation

Three horseshoe crabs were placed in the experimental group, and three in the control group. The horseshoe crab species was the southern horseshoe crab (*Tachypleus gigas*), obtained from Pusat Penternakan dan Penetasan Belangkas Sedili Kechil, which is a horseshoe crab centre in Johore, Malaysia. The horseshoe crabs were allowed to acclimatise to the system for two weeks so that the overall experimental setup was stabilised before the experiment began.

3.2 Experimental process

3.2.1 Experimental design

The experimental group consisted of a self-made filtration system. The control group consisted of a protein skimmer and an oxygen pump. Each group had 30.4 L of 27 ppt salt water and three horseshoe crabs. The experiment lasted for 15 days. Water quality indicators included ammonia concentration, salinity, and pH value. Horseshoe crab survival rate was assessed based on observation and the mass of the food consumed. Water quality was measured (based on water quality indicators stated above) and observed daily in the morning, and photos were taken of the experimental and control groups. Feeding was done at 8 a.m. with clams, and leftover food was removed at 3:30 p.m.

3.3.2 Data collection

Ammonia concentration in water was measured using an API ammonia concentration kit. The water sample was into a test tube of the test kit until it reaches the 5ml mark. Eight drops each of reagent one and reagent two were added sequentially. The mixture was shaken well and allowed to stand for 5 minutes. The test tube was then placed on a colour chart for observation and recording, as each colour on the chart corresponds to different ammonia concentration.

pH value of water was measured using a SERA pH kit. The water sample was into a test tube of the test kit until it reaches the 5ml mark. Four drops of reagent were added. The mixture was shaken well and the test tube was placed on a colour chart for observation and recording under natural light, as each colour on the chart corresponds to different pH value.

Salinity was measured using a Warmtone precision seawater hydrometer and salinity meter. Add the water sample to be tested to a level above the graduation mark and place it on a horizontal surface. The salinity was observed by keeping the line of sight level with the scale and recorded. The mass of food was measured before and after the experiment daily using an electronic scale, accurate to two decimal places. The difference in food mass was calculated, representing the mass of food consumed by the horseshoe crabs.

3.3 Others

Properly dispose of dead horseshoe crabs. Remove the dead horseshoe crabs floating on the surface of the water. Since we did not have biohazard bags, our group disinfected them, wrapped them up, and placed them in the trash can.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Self-made Filtration System Design Analysis

This subsection analyses the materials and equipment used in the self-made filtration system. When wastewater passes through the cotton cloth, it helps remove contaminants, suspended solids, and insect eggs. The use of cotton cloth is economical and environmentally friendly. The pebbles are the main part of the filter. When wastewater passes through the pebbles, they trap contaminants and impurities in the gaps between them, thus achieving filtration. A layer of sand (approximately 1-1.5 cm) serves as a habitat for juvenile horseshoe crabs, closely resembling their natural habitat. Fine sand was used in this experiment to facilitate burrowing and hiding in the sand, which are characteristics of horseshoe crabs. The filter screen has a structural function, supporting the pebbles as well as cloth in the filtration system and providing an outlet space for the water pipe within the tank. A 2mm mesh was chosen for the filter screen to maximise its function by allowing water to pass through while preventing pebbles and cloth from passing through. The water pipe serves as a water channel. The scouring pad acts as a filter, with its tiny gaps trapping residue that the pebbles cannot filter, making the filtration effect more significant. The water pump allows salt water to flow against gravity through the pipes into the filter, ensuring that the filtration system functions properly. The pumps used by the team are electrically operated. Electric water pumps have a longer lifespan and are more sustainable, besides being more economical as a result of their lower cost and maintenance expenses compared to traditional gasoline-powered water pumps.

4.2 Results (See Table 1 on Page 6)

4.3 Results Analysis

4.3.1 The Effect of Ammonia Concentration on Horseshoe Crab Mortality

Based on results shown in Table 1, the ammonia concentration in the control group increased from day 1 to day 5, and began to decrease from day 6. The ammonia concentration in the experimental group generally decreased during the 15-day experiment. This indicates that the self-made filtration system was more effective than the control group in reducing ammonia concentration of salt water.

The ammonia concentration in the control group ranged from 0 mg/L to 1.0 mg/L, with a difference of 1.0 mg/L. The ammonia concentration in the experimental group ranged from 0 mg/L to 0.50 mg/L, with a difference of 0.50 mg/L. This indicates that the self-made filtration system was more effective than the control group in maintaining ammonia concentration stability.

In the control group, the ammonia concentration spiked to 1.0 mg/L on day 5, and the mortality rate increased from 0% to 66.6% the following day. Afterward, the ammonia concentration decreased, and the mortality rate remained unchanged. In the experimental group, the ammonia concentration was 0.50 mg/L on day 1, and the mortality rate increased from 0% to 33.3% the following day. Afterward, the ammonia concentration decreased, and the mortality rate remained unchanged. This result indicates that ammonia concentration affects the mortality rate of horseshoe crabs. Higher ammonia concentrations lead to higher mortality rates. Recent studies have shown that high ammonia concentrations disrupt osmoregulation and impair respiratory function, leading to respiratory distress and death (Zawisza, 2024). Ammonia toxicity can cause systemic stress, organ damage, and impaired immune function, making horseshoe crabs more susceptible to infection and complications (Hans et al., 2018).

4.3.2 The Effect of Salinity on Horseshoe Crab Mortality

Based on results shown in Table 1, the salinity in the control group remained at 29 ppt for the first two days. The team adjusted the water to a salinity of 25 ppt. From day 3 to day 11, the salinity generally showed an upward trend, surging to 33 ppt on day 3. The team had its water adjusted to a salinity of 28 ppt. Overall, salinity is showing an upward trend. The experimental group's salinity was 31 ppt on day 1. The team had its water adjusted to 25 ppt. Subsequently, the salinity generally showed an upward trend. This result indicates that the overall salinity increased with the number of experimental days.

Recent studies have investigated salinity changes caused by water evaporation in aquarium environments, showing that water reduction as a result of evaporation leads to an increase in water salinity (Yu et al., 2021). Therefore, water evaporation is key to changes in salinity within the aquarium. During the experiment, the control group's salinity increased by an average of 1 ppt per day, while the experimental group's salinity increased by an average of 0.57 ppt per day. This result indicates that the homemade filtration system was more effective than the control group in maintaining salinity stability.

On day 1, the salinity in the experimental group was 31 ppt, and the mortality rate increased from 0% to 33.3% the following day. This result indicates that salinity has an impact on horseshoe crab mortality. The optimal salinity range for horseshoe crab survival is 25 to 30 ppt. Excessively high salinity can disrupt the osmotic regulation function of aquatic organisms (Bal & Paital, 2021).

4.3.3 The Effect of pH Value on Horseshoe Crab Mortality

Based on results shown in Table 1, the pH range of the control group was between 7.5 and 8.5, with a mode of 8.0 and a pH difference of 1.0. The pH range of the experimental group was between 8.0 and 9.0, with a mode of 8.0 and a pH difference of 1.0. This result indicates that the self-made filtration system and the control group had similar effects on maintaining pH stability.

On day 1, the pH of the experimental group was 9.0, and the mortality rate increased from 0% to 33.3% the following day. This result indicates that pH has an impact on horseshoe crab mortality. The suitable pH range for horseshoe crab survival is between 7.43 and 8.84 (Ng et al., 2021). Recent studies have shown that high pH values are harmful to marine organisms and can increase mortality (Sampaio et al., 2019; Pedersen & Hansen, 2003; Zhao et al., 2017).

4.3.4 Comprehensive Analysis

One of the objectives of this study was to investigate the impact of a self-made filtration system on the mortality rate of horseshoe crabs. The results in Table 1 showed that the mortality rate in the control group was 66.6%, while the mortality rate in the experimental group was 33.3%. This indicates that the self-made filtration system was more effective than the control group in improving the survival rate of horseshoe crabs. The water quality indicators measured in this study were ammonia concentration, salinity, and pH. Analysis of the results for each water quality indicator in both groups shows that, overall, the self-made filtration system was more effective than the control group in regulating and maintaining water quality stability. Water quality regulation and the maintenance of water quality stability are crucial for improving the survival rate of horseshoe crabs. This explains the results regarding the mortality rate of horseshoe crabs in the two groups.

Horseshoe crabs died twice in this study. The mortality rate increased from 0% to 66.6% in the control group between days 5 and 6, and from 0% to 33.3% in the experimental group between days 1 and 2. Before the deaths of the horseshoe crabs in the control group, both pH and salinity were within acceptable limits, indicating that the cause of death was excessively high ammonia concentration. Recent studies have investigated aquatic organisms and found that 0.537 mg/L is the upper limit of ammonia concentration for survival, and that ammonia concentrations above 0.6 mg/L can cause mortality in aquatic organisms (Ghufron et al., 2020). The cause of death in the experimental group was slightly high pH combined with relatively high salinity and ammonia concentration even though they are still within the tolerance range. Hence, based on the data, it is clear that the cause of death in the experimental group was influenced by multiple water quality indicators. Recent studies have shown that salinity has a limited impact on the survival of aquatic organisms within a specific tolerance range (Sampaio et al., 2019; Pedersen & Hansen, 2003; Zhao et al., 2017). In this study, considering both water quality and mortality rates, ammonia concentration played the most critical role in horseshoe crab mortality among the three water quality indicators used to infer the cause of death. Given that a self-made filtration system can effectively reduce

ammonia concentration, maintain water quality stability, and thus improve horseshoe crab survival rates, the objective of this experimental research is achieved.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The goal of this study was to fill a gap in existing research by investigating the impact of a novel filtration system on horseshoe crab mortality. The design and manufacture of this filtration system involved detailed steps, including fixing the filter mesh size, connecting water pipes, and adding sand.

Experimental results showed that the novel filtration system outperformed the traditional DoPhin PS2012 protein skimmer in several metrics, including ammonia concentration and salinity, while also exhibiting a relatively lower horseshoe crab mortality rate. Therefore, the research objective is achieved. Regarding the research hypothesis, the experimental results are consistent with the initial hypothesis that the novel filtration system outperformed in many metrics and resulted in a lower horseshoe crab mortality rate; therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

This study highlights the limitations of current filtration systems and the urgent need for research into innovative technologies. The results indicate that novel filtration systems play a crucial role in the conservation of horseshoe crabs and their ecosystems. Such systems hold promise for reducing horseshoe crab mortality, thereby positively impacting ecological balance. The experimental results show that the overall data of the experimental group has been more stable than that of the control group over a long period of time, which is also more in line with the living habits of horseshoe crabs.

For future research, it is suggested to explore the following potential directions: Firstly, further evaluate the applicability and effectiveness of novel filtration systems under different environmental conditions. Secondly, the research could be expanded to gain a deeper understanding of the filtration system's potential impact on other ecological factors in order to comprehensively assess its feasibility and ecological safety. However, since the pH data shows that protein skimmers are more effective, it indicates that both filtration systems have their advantages. Finally, improvements to the filtration system could be considered to enhance its efficiency and sustainability as well as adaptability to different aquatic environments.

Overall, this study provides strong support for the role of novel filtration systems in the conservation of horseshoe crabs as well as their ecosystems besides offering guidance for future research.

5.2 Limitations of The Study and Recommendations for Future Research

So far, the team believes there are several areas for improvement in this experiment.

1) Instability of Salinity Index:

The water-soluble salt index of both the experimental and control groups fluctuated continuously from day. To rectify this, our group suggests drawing a line at the initial water level and, when the water in the tank evaporates to a certain extent (approximately 3/4 of the original water), prepare salt solution using the salinity formula and add it to the tank until the water level reaches the line. Since only water evaporates from the tank, and salt does not evaporate at room temperature, our group infers that this method can maintain stable salinity within the tank.

2) Insufficient Sample Size:

Both the experimental and control groups only had one tank, insufficient to obtain the most accurate results. The team believes this problem can be solved by replicating the tanks used in the experimental and control groups. For the data, the average of all tanks in the experimental as well as control group will then be taken and the standard deviation will be calculated to obtain more accurate experimental data.

3) Inadequate Experimental Equipment:

Owing to budget constraints and the existence of relatively old experimental equipment, no more advanced equipment was purchased for this experiment. In response, the team believes that if the budget were sufficient, better experimental equipment could be purchased to increase the accuracy of the experiment and to investigate the cause of mortality in the horseshoe crabs.

4) Insufficient Experimental Time:

The experiment was conducted for only 15 days, which is insufficient to obtain the two sets of most accurate data. Our group suggests extending the experiment to 30 days or longer to observe more significant changes and obtain accurate data.

4.2 Results

Table 1 Changes in daily pH value, salinity (ppt), ammonia concentration (ppm), food weight (g), and mortality rate (%) in the experimental and control groups

Experimental Day	Data														
	Control Group							Experimental Group							
	pH Value (pH)	Salinity (ppt)	[Ammonia] (ppm)	Mortality (%)	Mass of Food (g)			pH Value (pH)	Salinity (ppt)	[Ammonia] (ppm)	Mortality (%)	Mass of Food (g)			
Before					After	Difference	Before					After	Difference		
Day 1	8.3	29	0.25	0.00	0.21	0.19	0.02	9.0	31	0.50	0.00	0.28	0.25	0.03	
Day 2	8.0	29	0.25	0.00	0.21	0.13	0.08	8.0	25	0.50	33.3	0.19	0.12	0.07	
Day 3	8.0	25	0.25	0.00	0.18	0.15	0.03	8.0	25	0.25	33.3	0.14	N/A	N/A	
Day 4	8.0	26	0.50	0.00	0.34	0.26	0.08	8.0	23	0.25	33.3	0.24	0.23	0.01	
Day 5	8.0	25	1.00	0.00	0.30	0.25	0.05	8.0	25	0.25	33.3	0.43	0.38	0.05	
Day 6	7.5	28	0.25	66.6	0.66	0.63	0.03	8.5	26	0.25	33.3	0.52	0.47	0.05	
Day 7	7.5	29	0.25	66.6	0.22	0.20	0.02	8.0	26	0.00	33.3	0.27	0.24	0.03	
Day 8	8.0	30	0.25	66.6	0.28	0.28	0.00	8.0	28	0.00	33.3	0.57	0.53	0.04	
Day 9	8.0	30	0.25	66.6	0.07	0.07	0.00	8.0	27	0.25	33.3	0.25	0.22	0.03	
Day 10	8.0	30	0.00	66.6	0.24	N/A	N/A	8.0	27	0.25	33.3	0.40	0.37	0.03	
Day 11	8.0	33	0.25	66.6	0.29	0.18	0.11	8.5	28	0.25	33.3	0.37	0.30	0.07	
Day 12	8.0	28	0.25	66.6	0.30	0.28	0.02	8.5	28	0.25	33.3	0.50	0.07	0.42	
Day 13	8.0	30	0.00	66.6	0.28	0.23	0.05	8.0	29	0.00	33.3	0.35	0.30	0.05	
Day 14	8.0	31	0.00	66.6	0.36	0.33	0.03	8.0	30	0.00	33.3	0.57	0.50	0.07	
Day 15	8.0	30	0.00	66.6	0.08	0.08	0.00	8.5	29	0.00	33.3	0.46	0.31	0.15	

* N/A means the data does not exist.

$$\text{Mass of Food Consumed} = (\text{Mass of Food After Experiment} - \text{Mass of Food Before Experiment}) \text{ g}$$

Table 2 Calculation of daily food intake for horseshoe crabs in the control and experimental groups

Calculations		
<p>Day 1: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.21 – 0.19) g = 0.02 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.28 – 0.25) g = 0.03 g</p> <p>Day 4: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.34 – 0.26) g = 0.08 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.24 – 0.23) g = 0.01 g</p> <p>Day 7: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.22 – 0.20) g = 0.02 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.27 – 0.24) g = 0.03 g</p> <p>Day 10: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.24 – N/A) g = N/A g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.40 – 0.37) g = 0.03 g</p> <p>Day 13: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.28 – 0.23) g = 0.05 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.35 – 0.30) g = 0.05 g</p>	<p>Day 2: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.21 – 0.13) g = 0.08 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.19 – 0.12) g = 0.07 g</p> <p>Day 5: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.30 – 0.25) g = 0.05 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.43 – 0.38) g = 0.05 g</p> <p>Day 8: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.28 – 0.28) g = 0.00 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.57 – 0.53) g = 0.04 g</p> <p>Day 11: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.29 – 0.18) g = 0.11 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.37 – 0.30) g = 0.07 g</p> <p>Day 14: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.36 – 0.33) g = 0.03 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.57 – 0.50) g = 0.07 g</p>	<p>Day 3: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.18 – 0.15) g = 0.03 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.14 – N/A) g = N/A g</p> <p>Day 6: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.66 – 0.63) g = 0.03 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.52 – 0.47) g = 0.05 g</p> <p>Day 9: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.07 – 0.07) g = 0.00 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.25 – 0.22) g = 0.03 g</p> <p>Day 12: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.30 – 0.28) g = 0.02 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.50 – 0.07) g = 0.42 g*</p> <p>Day 15: Mass of Food Consumed in Control Group = (0.08 – 0.08) g = 0 g Mass of Food Consumed in Experimental Group = (0.46 – 0.31) g = 0.15 g</p>

Note: * in data means larger pieces of clams were buried in the sand, making it impossible to measure the actual weight of the food consumed.

6. References

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